

Key Watch Ghana's Memorandum in relation to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

TO: Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal and
Parliamentary Affairs

FROM: Key Watch Ghana / Intersex Ghana

DATE: 29 September 2021

RE: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian
Family Values Bill, 2021

Honorable Members of Parliament:

Introduction

We at Key Watch Ghana and the Ghanaian Intersex community (Intersex Ghana Movement) wish to draw your attention to the current bill presented at the Ghanaian parliament, the current bill aims to protect Ghanaian family values, promote arbitrary harmful notions and provisions that violate the very basic fundamental human rights of people as stated in multiple Human Right treaties and conventions.

Intersex people are individuals born with any of several sex characteristics including chromosome patterns, gonads, or genitals that, according to the Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, "do not fit typical binary notions of male or female bodies". Though the range of atypical sex characteristics may be obvious from birth through the presence of physically ambiguous genitalia, in other instances, atypical characteristics may go unnoticed, presenting as ambiguous internal reproductive organs or atypical chromosomes that may remain unknown to an individual all of their life.

The notion of sex (gender) in the Ghanaian traditional setting has always been male and female. This fact has been unquestioned for several decades, but the biological gene

imbalances in persons that make it difficult to designate a sex for such person even to use the sex given to them at birth.

Some children's chromosomal sexuality contradicts their sexual characteristics and others have the physical traits of both sexes and of neither.

Preve 2003, drawing on life history and interviews with adults who were treated for intersexuality as children Sharon E. Preve explored how such individuals experience stigma and cope with being labelled as sexual deviants in a society that demands sexual conformity to the concept of MALE & FEMALE as is captured in the bill. We need to understand that intersex people go through different forms of abuses and suffer just because their genes conflict with their sex assigned at birth.

Criminalizing intersex people is same as criminalizing people born with disabilities, if one is to be punished for holding out as intersex, it is equal to criminalizing one holding out as being born blind or any other form of disability.

According to Routledge, 2020, impact of early sex assignments surgery on an individual's later life is examined based on clinical and ethical questions. The paper enlightens that non-consensual infant early sex assignment is based on powerful myths, taboos, and construction of gender-the perfect phallus.

Background

The current bill supports the practice of invasive, deeply traumatizing, irreversible harmful treatments on intersex infants and children that are unable to consent, and that are not at any danger to health or at any risk, such harmful and coercive medical interventions mainly intended to change the cosmetic appearance of genitalia have no genuine therapeutic purpose for the treatment and are often only performed only to minimize a (perceived) social stigma rather than any real medical concerns, such harmful interventions according to multiple accounts of the Intersex International organizations, and medical bodies are often followed by lifelong hormonal treatments, disability, chronic infections, sexual dysfunction, incontinency, sterility, chronic pain, and medical complications, compounded by shame, torture, and secrecy.

Analysis / Supporting Arguments

1. All human beings should be free from torture, ill-treatment, and harmful interventions

Clause 1 and 2, and clause 23 of the *Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021* advocates for the realignment of appropriate binary designations as determined by the medical practitioner, with surgical procedures, or in other terms coercive medical interventions on intersex persons.

Such provisions violate profoundly the rights that all humans must have bodily and mental integrity, freedom from torture and ill-treatment, and freedom from medical violence.

The right to security of the person, including freedom from injury to the body and the mind, or bodily and mental integrity is protected by the first substantive right in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, article 3, 7, 9,17, 24, and 26 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, and article 17 of the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

Forced and coercive medical interventions violate a right to health (including a right to free and informed consent), a right to legal capacity, and a right to non-discrimination.

The right to health includes the right that any individual has over their own health and body, including sexual and reproductive rights, freedom from interference, and the right to be free from torture, non-consensual medical intervention, and experimentation.

Ghana has an international legal obligation to protect all children from all forms of physical or mental violence, injury or abuse, neglect or negligent treatment, maltreatment, or exploitation. Ghanaian children have the right to freedom from violence, and freedom from torture and ill-treatment, and this bill contravenes these basic obligations.

When medical procedures take place on intersex persons, particularly on children and infants without personal informed consent, they violate the right to freedom from experimentation.

Ghana is obliged to take measures to abolish all types of harmful practices that are prejudicial to children's health, this bill does exactly the opposite, by criminalizing innate natural body variations and the right people have to learn more about their bodies and their experiences with their peers.

The Committee on the Rights of the Child has stated that assessments of a child's best interests must encompass the views of the child which include their participation in any decision about their bodily integrity and their mental integrity, any interpretations of a child's best interests based on social narrow views of gender cannot be used to justify practices that conflict with human dignity and the right to physical and mental integrity.

Ghana has the inherent obligation to eliminate all forced, coercive, and unnecessary medical interventions to modify variations of sex characteristics of intersex people and be indulgent to the violence perpetrated against intersex persons.

Multiple testimonies around the world and from Intersex Ghanaians have documented the profound and life-long negative impacts of these irreversible procedures, including permanent infertility/sterilization, incontinence, loss of sexual function and sensation, chronic pain, experiences tantamount to rape (such as dilation, the repeated insertion of a device into a newly opened vaginal cavity), causing life-long pain and severe psychological suffering, including depression and shame linked to attempts to hide and erase intersex traits.

As an intersex focused organization, we have highlighted concerns that children are frequently subjected not to one but an ongoing series of surgeries, treatments, follow-up treatments, to address complications that frequently arise, all of which are reported as painful and deeply traumatizing by many intersex persons who have undergone them. In addition, repeated genital exams, photography, and exposure, including in the context of training other medical professionals, have been experienced as deeply shaming, traumatic, and been described as a form of sexual abuse.

These surgeries as previously stated often leave intersex people sterile. In May 2014, the World Health Organization, the Office of the High Commissioner for Human Rights, UN Women, UNAIDS, UNDP, UNFPA and UNICEF issued a joint statement on eliminating forced, coercive, and otherwise involuntary sterilization, against intersex people.

In 2013, Juan Méndez, Special Rapporteur on torture and other cruel, inhuman, or degrading treatment or punishment remarked that such interventions result in “permanent, irreversible infertility and causing severe mental suffering”.

In 2018, Catalina Devandas-Aguilar, Special Rapporteur on the rights of persons with disabilities, remarked that there “are a growing number of treatments and interventions whose effectiveness is uncertain or deemed controversial” which “are invasive, painful and irreversible, and therefore may amount to torture or ill-treatment if applied involuntarily”

Such promotion for these coercive interventions as stated in clauses 1 and 2, and 23 of this bill clearly contravene with multiple basic fundamental human rights treaties and conventions that Ghana is abiding by.

2. Intersex is a natural manifestation of human bodily diversity in the human species.

Intersex is a term that relates to a broad range of innate physical traits or bodily variations that present naturally in humankind and fall outside of the stereotypical physio anatomical expectations for male or female bodies. Intersex people are born with physical, hormonal, or genetic features that are neither wholly female nor wholly male or a combination of female and male characteristics.

Intersex people have existed for as long as male or female human bodies has, and are part of nature, they are present in all cultures, ethnic groups, and across the human species, in the same way, other living beings in nature exist in harmony manifesting multiple forms of sexual bodily diversity, skin colours, body shapes, and heights, etc.

Many intersex variations exist; it is a spectrum or umbrella term, rather than a single category. Up to 45 different variations have been identified in human biology within that umbrella; sometimes these variations are obvious at birth, sometimes are identified at puberty, or later in adulthood, sometimes are never identified, yet can be genetically determined. Medical professionals have been using since 2006 a stigmatizing label, “*Disorders of Sex Development*”, to refer to intersex variations, a label that often promotes coercion, experimentation, and harm on intersex people.

According to the UN and several experts between 0.05% and up to 1.7% of the global population is born with intersex traits or with natural variations of sex characteristics.

Intersex variations can include differences in the number of sex chromosomes, different tissue responses to sex hormones, or different hormone balances. Examples of intersex variations include Androgen Insensitivity Syndrome (AIS), Congenital Adrenal Hyperplasia (CAH), and sex chromosome differences such as 47, XXY (often diagnosed as Klinefelter Syndrome) and 45, X0 (often diagnosed as Turner Syndrome).

People with intersex variations face severe human rights violations, mostly associated with deep-seated stigma, social notions, and harmful medical interventions explicitly intended to make intersex bodies conform forcibly to social norms for a specific sex or gender. On the other hand, this bill inappropriately places expectations that intersex people will openly challenge or transgress gender norms.

Intersex physiology is considered within the medical community as a medical condition with little or no consideration of the individual, and that particular view obscures the rights that every human being has to live freely without torture, harm, and ill-treatment, those prescribed “normalizing” surgeries on infants and children have the potential to impact other interrelated human rights, including the right to privacy (which extends to the right to personal autonomy/self-determination in relation to medical treatment); the right to equality and non-discrimination; and the prohibition against torture and other cruel, inhuman and degrading treatment (including the prohibition against non-consensual scientific or medical experimentation).

Intersex bodies are not the problem, the problem lies beneath social expectations of body normality.

3. The unnecessary medicalization, and the prohibition on the promotion of peer support and human rights affirming the health rights of intersex people.

Intersex people in Ghana might be furtherly subjected to more harmful medical practices that can inflict irreversible physical and psychological harm on them starting

in infancy, harms that can last throughout their lives.

Many of these procedures are done with the stated aim of making it easier for children to grow up “normal” and integrate into society by forcing them to conform to a particular sex assigned with a scalpel. However, on most occasions, the results of these interventions are often catastrophic, the supposed benefits are largely unproven, and there are generally no urgent health considerations at stake, only genital appearance “cosmetic genital plastic surgeries”.

These procedures that can be easily delayed until intersex children are old enough to decide whether they want them are being promoted by this bill to be performed on infants who then must live with the consequences of these decisions for a lifetime.

Furthermore clauses 1, 2, and 23, of this bill not only seeks to force these interventions, but it also attempts to criminalize the natural existence of bodily diversity by advocating at all costs for the unnecessary harm on intersex Ghanaians, particularly against infants and children, a practice that accounts in multiple forms as torture.

This bill also enables the state to persecute, erase, and eliminate the identity of intersex Ghanaians, people that have no agency over their identity and are just a manifestation of human biological diversity.

On the other hand, the bill prohibits intersex organizations from promoting the health rights of intersex children, infants, and adults, persons that have not agency over the manifestations of natural diversity in their bodies legitimizing further societal violence, stigma, erasure and constituting genocide against intersex people.

4. The rights of access to information and peaceful assembly.

Poor, inadequate, or partial information regarding the nature of a diagnosis, procedure or long-term outcomes, or the availability of peer support, violates the right to health and the right to access information and to free and informed consent.

Currently, this bill as prescribed prohibits the fundamental right for people born with

variations of their sex characteristics to peacefully assemble and provide life-saving psychosocial support to intersex people and their families.

For intersex people, peer support is vital, as it helps intersex people to connect with other intersex people and their families and share knowledge and experience about these body variations, health experiences, and psycho-social support from peers.

These interactions often lead to reduced stigma associated with one's intersex experience through education, support, and peer advice.

These interactions help intersex patients to encourage developments of appropriate health care and pursue evidenced medical pathways and guidelines for positive health experiences that are affirming of that natural bodily diversity.

When intersex people are allowed to gather and share their health experiences, they encourage a cycle of peer-based psychological support that also can help the families of intersex infants and children and their best interest for the future.

This has been particularly positive, for people that are born with differences in their bodily sex characteristics as living with biological differences in a stigmatizing society can create personal distress. This in turn can lead to secrecy and shame relating someone's body differences. However, this bill as presented is removing all possible psychosocial measures for assembly that intersex Ghanaians will have in the future, and this will only cause social isolation, exclusion, depression, and severe mental health issues.

We recommend

- That this bill is withdrawn altogether, since it clearly violates fundamental human rights stated in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), Convention against Torture, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women, and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.

- Nobody should violate these fundamental human rights by enacting provisions on national laws that advocate for medical practices that can be used to forcibly assign a “gender” are practices that violate a child's physical and bodily integrity, their right to protection from all forms of physical or mental violence, injury or abuse (CRC art. 19) and to the highest attainable standard of health (CRC art. 24), and ultimately their survival and development (CRC art. 6).
- This bill contravenes several articles of the Committee on the Rights of the Child, the CRC Committee has asserted multiple times that states should eliminate all types of non-consensual surgeries on intersex infants and children, given that these practices are a violation of their physical integrity and constitute a harmful practice.
- The Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) sets out obligations for states to recognize the human rights of children. The joint CRC and CEDAW has made multiple calls for the elimination of harmful practices against children and women and the Ghanaian government should abide by fundamental human rights international standards.
- The promotion of these surgeries by this bill without effective, independent oversight, and lacking a scientific basis as in the current proposition in the bill can only be categorized as torture (CRC art 10, 11, 12, and 13), disguised as normalizing medical interventions.
- No one should be subjected to unnecessary medical or surgical treatment during infancy or childhood, as it has been stated by the CRC, states need to guarantee the rights of children to bodily integrity, autonomy, and self-determination.
- Legislators must develop and implement transparent human rights and child rights-based legislative approaches that recognize that humans can be born with multiple layers of diversity.
- Ghana must stop criminalizing people for being born with a particular physical

body variation, as this clearly contravenes multiple human rights standards and contravenes multiple human rights treaties conventions related to torture and cruel, degrading, and inhuman treatment, right to health, privacy, the rights of the child, of women, and of persons with disabilities.

- Policymakers must prohibit medical practitioners and other professionals from conducting irreversible, non-vital, sex- “normalizing”, sex- “assigning” or sex altering surgical or other interventions, on a person’s physical sex characteristics unless the intersex person has provided personal, free and fully informed consent.
- Ghana’s legislator must take all possible measures to stop all types of harmful non-vital medical treatments and/or surgeries on intersex persons unless the intersex person itself is fully able to provide personal, free, and fully informed consent.
- Ghana’s legislators must ensure that intersex people and their families receive adequate counselling and support, particularly from other intersex peers. Intersex people shall have access to intersex affirmative human rights-based health care, psychosocial support and health care need covering fundamental vital needs, intersex people must be able to access appropriate impartial advice and care to give to parents and intersex children, being respectful of the intersex person’s autonomy, physical integrity and respecting the natural variations of their sex characteristics.

Who we are:

KEY WATCH GHANA is a non-governmental organization founded in 2015 and duly registered in Ghana, providing the services of socio-economic empowerment, human rights education and advocacy, reproductive health and sexual safety, with emphasis on Intersex persons and other marginalized groups.

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